

CURRENT ASPECTS OF VENEER APPLICATION IN ESTHETIC DENTISTRY (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Abstract. *In this article, the authors examine the concept and classification of veneers and provide a clinical evaluation of their significance in prosthetic dentistry. Veneers are thin prosthetic restorations bonded to the vestibular surface of teeth to restore their esthetic and functional characteristics. The use of veneers makes it possible to correct the shape, color, and position of teeth, as well as eliminate superficial defects of the hard dental tissues while preserving the maximum volume of healthy enamel, which corresponds to the principles of minimally invasive dentistry.*

Keywords: *prosthetic dentistry, ceramic veneers, porcelain veneers, veneer fixation, advantages of veneers.*

Introduction

Currently, esthetic dentistry is experiencing rapid development, offering patients increasingly advanced and minimally invasive methods for achieving an ideal smile. Since their introduction, veneer fabrication and application technologies have undergone significant changes, and today we can speak about new and relevant aspects that make them even more attractive. Veneers are thin, individually fabricated restorations that are bonded to the anterior surface of teeth, changing their color, shape, size, and even position. They are made from various materials; however, the most popular and aesthetically advanced are ceramic veneers (porcelain, lithium disilicate, zirconia). The aim of this review article is to systematize contemporary scientific data devoted to the analysis of veneer fixation and their clinical significance in prosthetic dentistry. The review is based on an analysis of current publications selected from international databases, including PubMed and PubMed Central (PMC), incorporating both systematic and narrative literature reviews.

Methodology of the literature analysis. To prepare this review, a targeted selection of scientific publications devoted to the analysis of veneer fixation and the main advantages of veneer application in esthetic dentistry was conducted. Inclusion criteria comprised review and systematic articles published within the last five years.

The search strategy was implemented using international scientific databases PubMed and PubMed Central (PMC). The following keywords and their combinations were applied: orthopedic dentistry, ceramic veneers, porcelain veneers, veneer fixation, veneer advantages. The search was limited to publications in English.

In contemporary prosthetic dentistry, veneers are classified according to several criteria reflecting the material of fabrication, the method of production, and the degree of tooth preparation. Such systematization allows the clinician to choose the optimal restorative option depending on the clinical situation, esthetic requirements, and functional load [1,2,6,11].

In studying the works of foreign authors Peumans M., Van Meerbeek B., Lambrechts P., Vanherle G. (2000), three main groups of porcelain veneers are distinguished (Table 1).

Table 1.

First group	High esthetics	Color stability and durability
Ceramic veneers	High	High stability, up to 10–15 years with proper care
Porcelain veneers	High	High stability, up to 10–15 years with proper care
Second group		
Zirconia veneers (based on zirconium dioxide)	Increased strength and resistance to mechanical loads	High stability, up to 10 years with proper care
Third group		
Composite veneers	High and can be fabricated directly in the oral cavity	Economically restores the esthetics of the dental arch but has lower durability

According to the method of fabrication, veneers are divided into direct and indirect types. Direct veneers are formed directly in the patient’s oral cavity using composite materials, which makes it possible to correct the shape and color of a tooth in a single visit. Indirect veneers are fabricated in a dental laboratory and most often represent ceramic or zirconia restorations. This method ensures a more precise fit and superior esthetic characteristics; however, it requires several visits to the dentist [1,2,3,4]. Studies by foreign researchers (Magne P., Belser U., 2002; Dalla Bona E., Peumans M., 2015; Scherrer S.S., 2017) confirm that classification according to the degree of tooth preparation divides veneers into three groups:

- No-prep veneers are minimally invasive and are used in cases of minor esthetic disturbances where preservation of tooth structure is essential [9,12,13];
- Minimally prepared veneers involve removal of a thin layer of enamel to improve adhesion and achieve optimal esthetics [9,12,13];
- Conventional veneers include preparation of enamel and partially dentin, providing reliable fixation and maximum esthetic outcomes in complex restorations [9,12,13].

Foreign authors such as McLaren E.A., Whiteman Y.Y. (2010) and McLaren E.A., White D. (2011) propose classifying veneers according to clinical indications. They distinguish restorations aimed at correcting tooth color and shape, closing diastemas and tremas, restoring damaged enamel, and treating minor defects of hard dental tissues. This approach allows consideration of individual patient characteristics and selection of the most appropriate type of veneer in each specific case [5,13,14].

Thus, the modern classification of veneers is multifaceted and takes into account the physical and chemical properties of materials, technological features of fabrication, and clinical indications. This makes individualized selection of restorations possible, ensuring high esthetic outcomes, functionality, and long-term durability of treatment. According to the method of fabrication, veneers are divided into direct and indirect types. Direct veneers are formed directly in the oral cavity, whereas indirect veneers are produced in a dental laboratory, allowing for a more accurate fit and enhanced esthetic properties of the restoration [2,7,8,9,10].

An important classification criterion is also the degree of preparation of hard dental tissues, according to which veneers are categorized into no-prep veneers, minimally prepared veneers, and conventional veneers with enamel preparation [11,12]. Veneers occupy an important place in modern prosthetic dentistry, as they effectively combine functional and esthetic rehabilitation of patients. The main clinical significance of veneers lies in their ability to restore the natural shape, color, and anatomical structure of teeth with minimal intervention into hard tissues. This is especially important in the smile zone, where esthetics is of primary importance [1,2].

The use of veneers allows solving a wide range of clinical tasks. These include correction of tooth discoloration caused by hypoplasia, fluorosis, or darkening after endodontic treatment; restoration of tooth shape in cases of diastemas, tremas, or enamel defects; and improvement of the overall contour of the dental arch. Such restorations ensure harmonious integration with natural teeth, creating a stable and long-lasting esthetic result [3,4]. In addition to their esthetic effect, veneers also have functional significance. With the correct selection of material and fixation method, they are capable of distributing masticatory load, preventing excessive enamel wear and reducing the risk of microcracks. Ceramic and zirconia veneers, due to their high strength, provide long-term reliability even under significant functional loads [2,5].

An important aspect of their clinical significance is the minimal invasiveness of the method. Unlike traditional crowns, veneers require only partial or minimal enamel preparation, which preserves natural tooth tissues, reduces the risk of complications, and increases patient satisfaction with the procedure [1,6]. Thus, the clinical significance of veneers in prosthetic dentistry is determined by their ability to provide simultaneous esthetic, functional, and structural rehabilitation of the dentition while minimizing intervention in natural tissues and enhancing the longevity of prosthetic restorations. This makes veneers one of the most востребованных (most in-demand) methods in modern esthetic dentistry.

A review of scientific literature confirms that in contemporary prosthetic dentistry veneers are widely used for esthetic rehabilitation of patients with tooth discoloration, shape anomalies, diastemas, tremas, and minor enamel defects. The high esthetic performance and durability of veneers are обусловлены (due to) the use of modern ceramic materials and adhesive systems [3,5]. Depending on the material of fabrication, veneers are classified into ceramic (porcelain), zirconia, and composite types. Porcelain veneers are characterized by high esthetics, biocompatibility, and color stability, making them the preferred choice in the smile zone [1,2]. Zirconia veneers, fabricated from zirconium dioxide, are distinguished by increased strength and resistance to functional loads; however, they require a specific approach to adhesive fixation [3,4]. Composite veneers are mainly used in clinical situations requiring rapid esthetic restoration or as a temporary solution [15,16,17].

Indications and Contraindications for Veneer Application

Veneers represent an essential tool in modern esthetic dentistry, enabling the solution of a wide range of clinical tasks with minimal intervention in tooth structures. The main indications for their application include:

- **Esthetic correction of tooth color** — veneers are indicated in cases of discoloration caused by hypoplasia, fluorosis, darkening after endodontic treatment, or staining from food and beverages. This allows achievement of a uniform and natural shade of the dental arch [1,2];

- **Correction of tooth shape and position** — veneers are used in cases of diastemas (interdental spaces), tremas, irregular dental arch contour, and slightly altered tooth morphology, providing a harmonious smile [3,4];
- **Restoration of enamel defects** — minor chips, cracks, erosions, or enamel wear can be compensated with veneers without extensive tooth preparation;
- **Functional rehabilitation** — veneers help restore the masticatory surface and distribute occlusal loads, especially when durable ceramic or zirconia materials are used [5].

Reversible Aspects of Veneer Application

Despite their high effectiveness, veneer application is associated with certain reversible aspects that should be considered in clinical practice:

Preservation of tooth structure. Unlike crowns, veneers require only minimal enamel preparation, preserving most natural tooth tissues and allowing replacement or correction of the restoration, if necessary, without significant damage [6].

Reversibility of the esthetic effect. In some cases, particularly with direct composite veneers, the restoration can be removed or replaced without compromising tooth integrity. This provides flexibility in clinical planning and allows esthetic modifications over time.

Temporary nature of certain restorations. Direct composite veneers may serve as a temporary solution, enabling evaluation of the esthetic outcome before placement of more durable ceramic or zirconia veneers [2,5].

Thus, indications for veneer application encompass both esthetic and functional aspects of dental rehabilitation, while the reversible characteristics of the method make it a conservative, safe, and flexible clinical tool.

Age-Related Indications and Contraindications

The application of veneers in prosthetic dentistry depends not only on clinical indications but also on patient age. Age is a significant factor influencing the choice of restoration method, material type, and fixation technique.

Age-Related Indications

Adolescence (16–18 years). Veneer placement is recommended after completion of occlusal formation and eruption of permanent teeth, typically by the age of 16–18. At this stage, indications include esthetic correction of tooth shape and color, closure of diastemas, and minor enamel defects [1,2].

Adulthood (18–50 years). This is the most common age group for veneer placement, as occlusion is fully formed and jaw growth is complete. Veneers are used to correct tooth color, restore shape and position, eliminate chips and enamel erosion, and improve overall smile esthetics [3,4].

Older age (over 50 years). Veneer placement remains possible; however, careful evaluation of hard dental tissues and periodontal condition is essential. In patients with pronounced tooth wear, gingival recession, or occlusal disorders, thorough functional and esthetic assessment is required prior to treatment [5].

Age-Related Contraindications

Childhood (under 16 years). Veneer placement is contraindicated because teeth and jaws are still developing, and permanent occlusion has not fully formed. Early veneer placement may lead to discrepancies in tooth size and occlusion, disruption of natural dental arch growth, and the need for frequent restoration replacement [1,2].

General Contraindications for Veneer Application. Despite their wide use in esthetic and functional dentistry, certain clinical situations limit veneer placement. Contraindications may be absolute or relative and involve both dental and systemic factors.

Absolute contraindication – insufficient enamel thickness.

Veneers require reliable adhesion to enamel. If enamel thickness is insufficient to ensure strong bonding, fixation may be unreliable, increasing the risk of debonding [1,2].

Analysis of Veneer Fixation and Clinical Complications

Veneer fixation is a critical stage directly affecting durability, strength, and esthetic outcomes. Contemporary studies emphasize that successful veneer placement depends on multiple factors: veneer material type, tooth surface preparation, selected adhesive system, and cement properties [1,2]. According to Peumans M. and co-authors (Van Meerbeek B., Lambrechts P., Vaherle G., 2000), the strength of the adhesive complex “veneer–cement–enamel” largely depends on micromechanical surface treatment of enamel and ceramic, proper etching, and use of primers. These procedures ensure reliable bonding and reduce the risk of restoration debonding [11,17,18].

Modern research using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) confirms that the microstructure of the adhesive interface plays a crucial role in veneer retention. Proper surface preparation and appropriate cement selection increase restoration longevity and minimize microcracks and marginal defects [2,3,22]. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses demonstrate that veneers bonded to enamel show higher survival rates and fewer complications compared to those bonded to dentin. The most common causes of debonding include errors in cementation technique, incompatibility between adhesive system and veneer material, and functional overload, such as in bruxism cases [3,19,20].

Furthermore, laboratory studies indicate that cement properties and seating pressure during fixation significantly influence bond strength. The use of modern adhesive systems and high-quality resin cements ensures long-term success, particularly with ceramic and zirconia veneers [21,22].

Conclusion

Thus, analysis of veneer fixation methods confirms that achieving a reliable and durable outcome requires consideration of a complex set of clinical and laboratory factors: tooth preparation, veneer material selection, adhesive system and cement choice, as well as control of functional loads. Contemporary adhesive technologies significantly reduce the risk of debonding and veneer failure, providing high esthetic and functional performance of restorations.

REFERENCES

1. Gavrilov E.I., Kalivradzhiyan E.S. Prosthetic Dentistry: National Guidelines. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media; 2018.
2. Zholudev S.E., Kuznetsov A.V. Modern ceramic materials in prosthetic dentistry. *Stomatologiya*. 2019;98(2):45–49.
3. Kulakov A.A., Lebedenko I.Yu. Prosthetic Treatment of Hard Dental Tissue Defects. Moscow: Meditsina; 2017.
4. Chikunov S.O. Repeated rehabilitation of patients after previously performed prosthetic dental treatment: Dissertation of Doctor of Medical Sciences: 14.01.14, 19.00.04. Saint Petersburg; 2014. 323 p.

5. Addison O., Marquis P.M., Fleming G.J. Adhesive luting of all-ceramic restorations—the impact of cementation variables and short-term water storage on the strength of a feldspathic dental ceramic. *Journal of Adhesive Dentistry*. 2008;10:285–293.
6. Agathian R., Manoharan P.S., Rajkumar E. Indirect resin composite – A literature review. *Journal of Advanced Clinical & Research Insights*. 2021.
7. Azeem R.A., Sureshbabu N.M. Clinical performance of direct versus indirect composite restorations in posterior teeth: A systematic review. *Journal of Conservative Dentistry*. 2018;21(1):2–9. doi:10.4103/JCD.JCD_213_16.
8. Blatz M.B., Sadan A., Kern M. Resin-ceramic bonding: a review of the literature. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2003;89(3):268–274.
9. Dalla Bona E., Peumans M. Clinical indications and preparation designs for ceramic veneers. *Journal of Adhesive Dentistry*. 2015;17(5):391–402.
10. Kelly J.R., Benetti P. Ceramic materials in dentistry: historical evolution and current practice. *Australian Dental Journal*. 2011;56(Suppl 1):84–96.
11. Peumans M., Van Meerbeek B., Lambrechts P., Vanherle G. Porcelain veneers: a review of the literature. *Journal of Dentistry*. 2000;28(3):163–177.
12. Magne P., Belser U. Bonded Porcelain Restorations in the Anterior Dentition: A Biomimetic Approach. Chicago: Quintessence Publishing; 2002.
13. McLaren E.A., Whiteman Y.Y. Ceramics: rationale for material selection. *Compendium of Continuing Education in Dentistry*. 2010;31(9):666–676.
14. McLaren E.A., White D. Digital shade matching and color stability in ceramic veneers. *Compendium of Continuing Education in Dentistry*. 2011;32(6):50–58.
15. Jurado C., Fages M., Giner L. Clinical survival and complication rate of ceramic veneers bonded to different substrates: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2025;133(2):145–158.
16. Stawarczyk B., Liebermann A., Eichberger M., Hämmerle C.H. Fracture load of zirconia anterior veneers: influence of thickness and surface treatment. *Clinical Oral Investigations*. 2014;18(7):1705–1712.
17. Scherrer S.S., et al. Effect of adhesive systems and surface treatments on zirconia bonding. *Dental Materials*. 2017.
18. Chaar M., Kern M. Clinical complications and survival of zirconia veneers: a review. *Quintessence International*. 2020;51(5):390–398.
19. Van Meerbeek B., et al. State of the art of self-etch adhesives. *Dental Materials*. 2003.
20. Litonjua L.A., et al. Effect of curing protocol and resin cement on bond strength to enamel and dentin. *Operative Dentistry*. 2005.
21. Jurado C., Fages M., Giner L. Clinical survival and complication rate of ceramic veneers bonded to different substrates: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry*. 2025;133(2):145–158.
22. The Success of Dental Veneers According to Preparation Design and Material Type. *PubMed Central (PMC)*. 2018. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6311473>